

EFFECT OF A TIP CLEARANCE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF A LOW SPEED CENTRIFUGAL COMPRESSOR

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ABSTRACT

Tip clearance effects on flow field of a low speed centrifugal compressor without and with partial shroud (PS) attached to the rotor blade tip at three values of tip clearance, viz. $\phi = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% of rotor blade height at the exit at three flow coefficients, namely, $\phi = 0.12, 0.18$ (below design flow coefficient), $\phi = 0.28$ (design flow coefficient) and $\phi = 0.34$ (above design flow coefficient), is analysed computationally using structured multi block grid with fine grid in the tip clearance region. The paper aims to study several flow characteristics between blade channels using commercial flow solver ANSYS CFX 15.0 based on finite volume techniques. The centrifugal compressor in aerodynamic requirement is that edge velocities along the impeller channel passage surfaces like hub, shroud, pressure and suction surfaces vary smoothly without sudden decelerations, which cause flow separation leading to losses. Using the periodic boundaries and defined flow conditions at inflow / exit flow and blade rotations, the turbulent viscous flow between blade channels are computed. The efficiency related parameters using average quantities, besides flow pattern in terms of velocities, streamlines and pressure distribution on blade surfaces are graphically interpreted. An attempt is also made to study the influence of pressure loads on structural deformations in the chosen blade profile. This paper highlights aero-mechanical features of centrifugal impeller obtained from several numerical simulations, which are expected to provide a sound basis for further investigations.

Key words: Centrifugal compressor, Flow coefficient, Partial shroud attached to the rotor blade tip, Streamlines, passage wake.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The centrifugal compressors have a wide range of applications especially for power plants for small aircraft and helicopters, in process industries, compression of gases and vapours, because they can provide high-pressure ratios and large operating ranges with relatively high efficiencies. Centrifugal compressors are used primarily for their suitability for handling small volume flows, but other advantages include a shorter length than an equivalent axial flow compressor, less susceptibility to loss of performance by buildup of deposits on the blade surfaces and their suitability to operate over a wide range of mass flow. The gas turbine engines powering the most passenger and military aircrafts are also called jet engines. Tip clearance in centrifugal compressor causes the leakage of high pressure fluid from pressure surface to suction surface of the impeller blade, making the flow field highly complex and effecting the performance. In centrifugal compressor due to the low efficiency and thrust to weight ratio, they are limited to short range applications. However, the inability for spark ignition engines to work at high altitude warrants further development to improve the efficiency of these miniature gas turbines. Hayami (1997) has found from his experiments that axial movement of the casing has better efficiency over the movement of casing in radial and axial directions. Radial movement of casing increases clearance at inducer, which reduces the operating range. The tipclearance studies are conducted to understand the flow behavior in order to minimise the effect of tip clearance. Pampreen (1973), Mashimo et al. (1979), Sitaram and Pandey (1990) have conducted experimental studies and suggested that by reducing the tip clearance gap size, the tip clearance effect can be minimised.

2. MODELING OF COMPRESSOR BLADES

The design details of the impeller which is used in the present investigation are given below:

- | | |
|---|---|
| Inducer hub diameter, $d_{ih} = 160$ mm | Inducer tip diameter, $d_{it} = 300$ mm |
| Impeller tip diameter, $d_2 = 500$ mm | Blade height at the exit, $b_2 = 34.7$ mm |
| No. of blades of impeller, $N_b = 16$ | Blade angle at inducer hub, $\beta_{ih} = 53^\circ$ |
| Blade angle at inducer tip, $\beta_{it} = 35^\circ$ | Blade angle at exit, $\beta_2 = 90^\circ$ |
| Thickness of the blade, $t = 3$ mm | Rotor speed, $N = 2000$ rpm |
- All angles are with respect to the tangential direction.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of centrifugal compressor setup and blade to blade view

Schematic diagram of centrifugal compressor setup as shown in fig.1. The geometric model used for the computational simulation of Centrifugal impeller with above specifications with 3mm thickness throughout the blade for generation of three dimensional blades was done as shown in Fig. 2. A single passage of the impeller with inlet at 50mm ahead of the impeller and outlet at a distance of 35mm downstream of impeller is shown in Fig. 3. Casing is designed with 0.7mm clearance throughout the blade height. Three tip clearances of 2.2%, 5.1% and 7.9% of trailing edge blade height are obtained by moving the casing axially. ANSYS CFX 15.0 version software is used for obtaining the solution and standard k-ε turbulence model is used for the closure. The computational domain is kept at 50 mm ahead of the eye inlet of the impeller in order to ensure that the inlet boundary conditions are not affected by the back pressure of impeller blade. The blade gen layout with construction features related to wrapper angle, number of blades, angles distribution and blade thickness for generation of three dimensional blades was done in order to carry out structural analysis of the blade surfaces the software provided export options to generate computational mesh accounting blade thickness is also explored in static structural analysis package. The blade profiles generated in the software mentioned above module are imported to template based multi-block structured computational mesh software module called turbo grid. After these operations three dimensional computational mesh generation process for compressor blade with boundary patches, periodic surfaces are created.

Figure 2 Centrifugal compressor (without and with PS)

Figure 3 Computational domain of single passage (with and without PS)

3. COMPUTATIONAL METHODOLOGY

Most fluid flow simulation technology uses completely different meshing, loading and solving methods compared to CFD simulation. And this is where the true power of Workbench 15.0 comes into play. When the user is connecting up the dialogs within the schematic layouts, many of these are handled automatically, simply by dragging a connection between the outputs of one analysis system and the inputs of another. The geometry from either of the CAD Systems and Blade Gen Model can be connected to simulation model before setup option is activated. The next step is to generate the meshing solid body for which several methods are provided in ANSYS Workbench 15.0 these tools have the benefit of being highly automated along with having a moderate to high degree of user control. Upon startup of the meshing application meshing options panel displays, which allows you to quickly and easily set your meshing preferences based on the physics you are preparing to solve. In CFX we have to use turbo mode for this problem statement, with respective to this stationary, rotating components are defined. The density going to vary compressible fluid with pressure fluid properties kept as air ideal gas. Reference pressure is 1 atm. Heat transfer is calculated by total energy because increase in density causes to increase in temperature and because of rotational energy it will try to change the heat transfer rate, in total energy methods only all this effects will get considered. Shear Stress Transport Turbulence model was used because of near wall treatment is required and presence of ad-versed pressure gradient. Inlet and outlet boundaries are pressure inlet with 0 Pa gauge pressure and mass flow 0.087 Kg/s at outlet respectively. Rotating domain interface used as Stage. The stage averaging at the frame change interface incurs a one-time mixing loss. This loss is equivalent to assuming that the physical mixing supplied by the relative motion between components is sufficiently large to cause any upstream velocity profile to mix out prior to entering the downstream machine component. Stage analysis is most appropriate when the circumferential variation of the flow is of the order of the component pitch stage for interfaces used for steady state simulations. Physical Time scaling value was observed to be taken as 10^{-3} s. Accuracy criteria of RMS solution was decreased to 10^{-5} for better accuracy.

Table 1 Mesh statistics

Statistics	
<input type="checkbox"/> Nodes	445604
<input type="checkbox"/> Elements	2310116
Mesh Metric	Skewness
<input type="checkbox"/> Min	7.666276246443E-05
<input type="checkbox"/> Max	0.797751114670892
<input type="checkbox"/> Average	0.233106168038319
<input type="checkbox"/> Standard Deviation	0.12186113343001

Frequency of distribution of skewness

Figure 4 Three dimensional mesh for single compressible blade row and streamlines from the inlet of impellor around the blades

3.1. Validations for Tip Clearance

Prior to comparing the performance of the test cases, the numerical result for the three values of tip clearances ($\tau=2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9%), was validated with the experimental data. Measurements were carried out with steady probes and scanning box (Model FC091-3) and micro manometer (model FCO12). Experimental results were validated by comparing the computed characteristic curves of the efficiency and energy coefficient with the experimental data, static pressure from inlet to outlet of the blade with the computational data. The CFD results showed satisfactory agreement with the experimental results over the full range of operating conditions. The overall flow structure predicted by the numerical simulations, including the jet-wake flow pattern, was qualitatively well captured, as observed by comparison with the experimental results. Improved results may be obtained with PS.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Performance Characteristics: Effect of Configuration: The effect of the two configurations on the performance of the centrifugal compressor in Figure 5 shows the performance characteristic in terms of energy coefficient, ψ vs. flow coefficient, ϕ for the three values of tip clearance for both configurations. At all values of tip clearance, PS gives higher value of energy coefficient, as the partial shroud obstructs the tip leakage flow and allows it to mix with main flow at a further distance. It may be observed that the performance of the rotor without PS at $\tau=2.2\%$ is almost similar to that the rotor with PS at $\tau=5.1\%$. Hence by using partial shroud the rotor can operate at higher clearances with mechanical safe margins but without sacrificing performance. Figure 6 shows the performance characteristic in terms of efficiency, η vs. flow coefficient, ϕ for the three values of tip clearance for both configurations. At all values of tip clearance, PS gives higher value of efficiency compared to that without PS due to reduced tip leakage flows. In fact the efficiency of the rotor with PS even at the highest value of tip clearance observed is higher than the efficiency of the rotor without partial shroud at the lowest value of tip clearance.

Effect of Tip Clearance: Effect of tip clearance of a low speed centrifugal compressor computational investigation results can be concluded that partial shroud is very beneficial to the performance of the compressor. In order to determine the effect of tip clearance on the performance of the compressor with and without partial shroud means, the performance curves in terms of ψ vs. ϕ and η vs. ϕ are plotted for the two configurations, viz., without PS, and with PS only for the three values of tip clearances observed, i.e. $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% . The ψ vs. ϕ curve shows that the operating range of the compressor is increased, for the basic configuration, as the tip clearance is increased. The result of the numerical investigations revealed that, energy coefficient across the compressor is reduced as the tip clearance is increased.

Figure 5 Performance of the centrifugal compressor: ψ vs. ϕ curve

Figure 6 Performance of the centrifugal compressor: η vs. ϕ

4.1. Velocity Vectors at Outlet

A velocity vector at the exit of the impeller is shown in figure 7. The fluid flows with PS on tip of the blade velocities are high on suction surface than pressure surface because of blade curvature. With increase in tip clearance, the velocity on both pressure side and suction side is decreasing. For $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% clearance for without PS. Configuration with PS, high velocity of the fluid above the blade from pressure side to suction side through tip clearance is observed. The velocity distribution at outlet is minimum near hub and casing indicating the boundary layer, velocity is observed near the casing, indicating higher energy transfer near casing. Velocity for 5.1% , 7.9% tip clearance have more velocity at the outlet than 2.2% tip clearance with partial shroud indicating loss of static pressure at outlet.

Velocity vectors at exit of the blade for 2.2% clearance for without PS and with PS

Velocity vectors at exit of the blade for 5.1% clearance for without PS and with PS

Velocity vectors at exit of the blade for 7.9% clearance for without PS and with PS

Figure 7 Velocity vectors at exit of the blade for $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% clearance for without PS and with PS

4.2. Static Pressure Contours at Span 0.7

Static pressure contours in blade to blade view, at span 0.7 are shown in figure 8. The contours show gradual pressure rise from inlet to outlet of the compressor due to dynamic action of the rotating impeller. Gradual increase of static pressure from inlet to outlet is clearly observed at all tip clearances i.e. $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% clearance. With PS on tip of the blade, low pressure change is observed. But without PS on tip of the blade, the pressure at outlet is reduced. High pressure on pressure side of the blade and low pressure on suction side of the blade are observed at all tip clearances. With increase in tip clearance, reduction in pressure on both pressure side and suction side is found.

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Static pressure contours for 2.2% clearance at mid span without PS and with PS

Static pressure contours for 5.1% clearance at mid span without PS and with PS

Static pressure contours for 7.9% clearance at span 0.7 without PS and with PS

Figure 8 Static pressure contours for $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% clearance at mid span without PS and with PS

4.3. Velocity Contours at Span 0.7

Velocity contours in blade to blade view, at span 0.7 is shown in figure 9. The velocity contours show improved velocities on suction side with PS. With PS on tip of the blade, the low velocity region is reducing and also velocity improvement is observed. The contours show improved velocities on suction side with partial shroud. The low velocity passage wake area on suction side of the blade is reducing with PS on tip of the blade. At 2.2% clearance, velocities are more near the suction side shroud corner and relative velocities are low near pressure side hub corner. Due to the centrifugal forces and curvature, velocity on suction side is higher than pressure side. For other clearances, leakage of flow from pressure side to suction side of the blade through the tip gap is observed. Vertical flow near the suction side of the blade meets the tip leakage flow near suction side shroud corner. Outlet to inlet pressure ratio at different

flow coefficients is increase in pressure ratio with PS on tip of the blade is observed at all flow coefficients. But without PS on tip of the blade, reduction in pressure ratio is observed at all flow coefficients because of more fluid leakage through the basic configuration.

Velocity contours for 2.2% clearance for without PS and with PS

Velocity contours for 5.1% clearance for without PS and with PS

Velocity contours for 7.9% clearance for without PS and with PS

Figure 9 Velocity contours for $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% clearance at span 0.7 for without PS and with PS

Blade loading: Blade loading charts at design for 2.2% tip clearance at without PS and with PS were shown in fig. 11. Fluid flow without PS and with PS on tip of the blade, significant change in pressure on suction side is observed. Low static pressure on suction and high pressure on pressure side of the blade is observed. With increase in tip clearance, static pressure on both pressure side and suction side are reducing.

Figure 10 Blade loading for 2.2% clearance at without and with partial shroud

Static Pressure Distribution: Static pressure distribution along stream wise direction from inlet to outlet is shown in figure 12. This plot indicated that the pressure from inlet to the outlet of the compressor is increasing gradually along the stream wise direction due to the dynamic head developed by the rotating impeller. A drop in static pressure near stream wise direction of 0.2 is observed at 2.2% tip clearance due to the acceleration of the flow in to the eye of the impeller. Static pressure reduction is observed with PS on tip of the blade. With PS on tip of the blade, static pressure at outlet is more than the static pressure at basic configuration.

Figure 11 Pressure inlet to outlet over stream wise for 2.2% clearance without and with PS

5. CONCLUSIONS

Tip clearance effects on flow field of a low speed centrifugal compressor without and with partial shroud (PS) attached to the rotor blade tip at three values of tip clearance, viz. $\tau=2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% of rotor blade height at the exit at four flow coefficients, namely, $\phi=0.12$, 0.18 (below design flow coefficient), $\phi=0.28$ (design flow coefficient) and $\phi=0.34$ (above design flow coefficient), is analyzed computationally in the tip clearance region. Effect of tip clearance of a low speed centrifugal compressor computational investigation results can be concluded that partial shroud is very beneficial to the performance of the compressor, for both the configurations. In order to determine the effect of tip clearance on the performance of the compressor with and without passive means, the performance curves in terms of ψ vs. ϕ and η vs. ϕ are plotted for the two configurations, viz., without PS, and with PS only for the three values of tip clearances observed, i.e. $\tau = 2.2\%$, 5.1% and 7.9% . Static pressure contours in blade to blade view, at span 0.7 is the gradual pressure rise from inlet to outlet of the compressor due to dynamic action of the rotating impeller. The velocity contours show improved velocities on suction side with PS. With PS on tip of the blade, the low velocity region is reducing and also velocity improvement is observed.

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